

RELIGIOUS LIBERTY IN A PANDEMIC: CONSTITUTIONAL CHALLENGES TO MASS GATHERING BANS

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ABSTRACT: The coronavirus pandemic led to an unprecedented shutdown of the United States. To stem the spread of the highly contagious pathogen, much of the country shut down for at least a month in April 2020, with the vast majority of governors ordering people to stay at home as much as possible.² When cases surged again in the United States, some states reinstated those orders. The emergency regulations usually included a ban on large gatherings, such as any in-person gathering of more than ten people. Although some states exempted worship services, others did not.³ Churches sued, arguing that these bans violated their Free Exercise Clause rights by treating worship services more strictly than analogous activities that were not banned, such as shopping at a supermarket or superstore—allowed as essential services. This essay examines these claims, concluding that the constitutionality of the bans turns on the science of how the pathogen spreads, and that the best available scientific evidence supports the mass gathering bans.

KEYWORDS: religious liberty, COVID-19, churches, bans,

I. JACOBSON OR SMITH?

Some courts faced with religious liberty challenges to COVID-19 mass gathering bans have eschewed traditional constitutional analysis, arguing that emergency circumstances call for more deferential review.⁴ In support, they cite the Supreme Court ruling in *Jacobson v. Massachusetts*, a 1905 Supreme Court case affirming mandatory vaccination during a smallpox epidemic.⁵

The Supreme Court was originally divided. Before Amy Coney Barrett was appointed as the newest Supreme Court Justice, the Supreme

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2. Jiachun Wu et al., *Stay-at-Home Orders Across the Country*, NBC News (Apr. 29, 2020), <https://www.nbc-news.com/health/health-news/here-are-stay-home-orders-across-country-n1168736>.

3. Jack Jenkins, *See Which States Have Religious Exemptions in Their Stay-at-Home Orders*, Religious News Service (Apr. 9, 2020), <https://religionnews.com/2020/04/09/see-which-states-have-religious-exemptions-in-their-stay-at-home-orders/>.

4. *See, e.g.,* *Elim Romanian Pentecostal Church v. Pritzker*, 962 F.3d 341 (7th Cir. 2020).

5. *Jacobson v. Commonwealth of Massachusetts*, 197 U.S. 11 (1905).

Court twice rejected challenges by churches to COVID-19 regulations.⁶ In a concurrence, Chief Justice Roberts explicitly cited *Jacobson* with approval.⁷ However, since then the newly configured Court struck down COVID-19 regulations more than once with no mention of *Jacobson* in the per curiam decisions.⁸ Indeed, in one, Justice Gorsuch devoted a significant part of his concurrence to attacking *Jacobson*.⁹

I am also wary of lowering constitutional scrutiny, even during a devastating pandemic. It makes it too tempting for the government to use the emergency as a pretext to limit rights; states have already successfully invoked the pandemic to curtail women’s constitutional right to abortion.¹⁰ Instead, the current doctrine articulated by *Employment Division v. Smith*, should control.¹¹ Under *Smith*, government regulations that are neutral and generally applicable do not violate the Free Exercise Clause, even if they do limit people’s ability to practice their religion.

II. NEUTRAL & GENERALLY APPLICABLE

An order is neutral if it does not target religion, and it is generally applicable if it applies broadly to the relevant population. While neutrality and general applicability are separate inquiries, the two issues are interrelated.

A. NEUTRALITY

The neutrality requirement is meant to capture discriminatory targeting of religion. According to the Supreme Court, the touchstone of neutrality is whether “the object of [the] law is to infringe upon or restrict practices *because of* their religious motivation.”¹²

At a minimum, a neutral law must be neutral on its face. A ban on all mass gatherings, whether religious or secular, is neutral on its face. However, neutrality is not limited to facial neutrality, and some courts infer hostility if religious conduct is treated differently from its secular counterparts.

If the true secular counterparts are other mass gatherings, then there is no discrimination: No hostility toward religion can be gleaned from ban-

6. *S. Bay United Pentecostal Church v. Newsom*, 140 S. Ct. 1613 (2020); *Calvary Chapel Dayton Valley v. Sisolak*, 140 S. Ct. 2603 (2020).

7. *S. Bay United Pentecostal Church v. Newsom*, 140 S. Ct. 1613 (2020) (Roberts, C.J., concurring).

8. *Roman Catholic Diocese of Brooklyn v. Cuomo*, 141 S. Ct. 63 (2020); *Tandon v. Newsom*, 141 S. Ct. 1294 (2021).

9. *Roman Catholic Diocese of Brooklyn v. Cuomo*, 141 S. Ct. 63 (2020) (Gorsuch, J., concurring).

10. See, e.g., *In re Abbott*, 954 F.3d 772, 784–85 (5th Cir. 2020) (upholding ban on nonemergency abortions under *Jacobson* standard).

11. *Employment Division v. Smith*, 494 U.S. 872 (1990).

12. *Church of the Lukumi Babalu Aye, Inc. v. City of Hialeah*, 508 U.S. 520, 533 (1993) (italics added).

ning all gatherings of a certain size, whether they be in restaurants, bars, movie theatres, sports arenas, gyms, or houses of worship.

B. GENERALLY APPLICABLE

General applicability is another way to ferret out discriminatory treatment of religion. The idea is that “government, in pursuit of legitimate interests, cannot in a selective manner impose burdens only on conduct motivated by religious belief.”¹³ That is, the government cannot accomplish its goals at the expense of religious organizations alone. When religious conduct must bear the cost, but not secular conduct that “endangers [the government’s] interests in a similar or greater degree,”¹⁴ a law is not generally applicable.

Although a law wouldn’t be generally applicable if it only limited large religious gatherings but not large secular ones, a ban on all mass gatherings does not have that problem.

Churches, however, argue that this is exactly what happened under the shutdown orders, which barred worship services while myriad other comparable activities, like shopping at grocery, garden, and box stores, were permitted. Nonetheless, these activities are distinguishable.

1. ESSENTIALNESS

The activities may or may not be distinguishable in terms of essentialness. Some courts have argued that the exempted activities were essential in the sense that people could not do without them. For example, a few courts have argued that the exempted activities like food shopping are essential to survival in a way that church is not: “All these stores facilitate the purchase of necessary items that help treat ill individuals who are staying at home, or that make a house habitable, or that feed people so they can stay alive.”¹⁵ This conclusion arguably embeds a contested value judgment about what is essential to human flourishing. To valorize physical needs over spiritual ones may not adequately express everyone’s priorities.

Other courts have argued that the exempted activities are essential in the sense that there are no alternatives available.¹⁶ We must eat, yet most

13. *Church of the Lukumi Babalu Aye*, 508 U.S. at 543.

14. *Church of the Lukumi Babalu Aye*, 508 U.S. at 543.

15. *Legacy Church, Inc. v. Kunkel*, 455 F. Supp. 3d 1100, 1160 (D.N.M. 2020).

16. *Antietam Battlefield KOA v. Hogan*, 461 F. Supp. 3d 214, 231 (D. Md. 2020), appeal dismissed, No. 20-1579, 2020 WL 6787532 (4th Cir. July 6, 2020) (“[U]nlike religious services, [these essential services] cannot operate remotely.”).

of us cannot grow our own food and therefore must purchase it from a supermarket. For those who must worship, alternatives to in-church services abound. People may pray to God on their own at home or together outside, online, or at drive-in services. To be sure, the experience is not exactly the same as in-person fellowship, but little in our lives today is exactly the same.

There are rebuttals and counter-rebuttals to both claims. Although people must buy food, why not have it delivered rather than purchase it in person? Of course, that assumes both the availability and affordability of delivery services, which simply may not be the state of affairs for all people and for all stores. At the same time, even if most religions do not mandate that worship take the form of large in-person gatherings, perhaps a few do.

2. HEALTH RISK

Ultimately whether these two activities can be distinguished on the basis of essentialness does not matter because they are distinguishable based on the health risks attached to them. That is, when it comes to the reason why the bans were imposed-- to limit the spread of the coronavirus-- these activities are not comparable. The risk of spreading the coronavirus is much higher at a worship service compared to shopping. Although the Supreme Court has held otherwise, it does not have science on its side.

Studies have established that people are contagious even before they exhibit symptoms,¹⁷ and that the coronavirus spreads mainly by person-to-person contact via droplets and aerosols.¹⁸ As a result, the risks of transmission appear greatest in crowded indoor spaces where people are interacting with each other for longer periods of time, especially where

17. Tina Hesman Saey, *Covid-19 May Be Most Contagious One or Two Days Before Symptoms Appear*, Science News (Apr. 15, 2020, 5:39 PM), <https://www.sciencenews.org/article/coronavirus-covid-19-infection-contagious-days-before-symptoms-appear> (noting that individuals are most likely to spread Covid-19 before they feel ill); Christie Aschwanden, *How 'Superspreading' Events Drive Most COVID-19 Spread*, Scientific America (June 23, 2020), <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/how-superspreading-events-drive-most-covid-19-spread1> (reporting that roughly 40 percent of transmission occurs before the person shows symptoms according to CDC estimates).

18. Tanya Lewis, *How Coronavirus Spreads Through the Air: What We Know So Far*, SCIENTIFIC AMERICA (May 12, 2020), <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/how-coronavirus-spreads-through-the-air-what-we-know-so-far1/>; Apoorva Mandavilli, *The Coronavirus Can Be Airborne Indoors*, W.H.O. Say, N.Y. TIMES (Oct. 5, 2020), <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/07/09/health/virus-aerosols-who.html>; Trisha Greehalgh et al., *Ten Scientific Reasons in Support of Airborne Transmission of SARS-CoV-2*, 297 THE LANCET 1603 (Apr. 15, 2021), [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(21\)00869-2/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(21)00869-2/fulltext)

the ventilation is poor.¹⁹ The World Health Organization advises people to “Avoid the Three Cs: Confined and enclosed places, Crowded places, and Close-contact settings.”²⁰

Singing and speaking are also risk factors.²¹ One of the most notable early outbreaks in the United States was traced to a choir rehearsal at a church. Even though the singers took care to apply hand sanitizer and observe social distancing, 53 out of 61 contracted COVID-19.²² But even speaking loudly can significantly increase the risk of transmission.²³

In fact, religious services have been the vector for multiple coronavirus outbreaks.²⁴ One CDC Study found that after two positive but asymptomatic worshippers attended church events, at least 35 of 92 attendees fell ill, with three dying. Moreover, at least 26 more cases in the community could be traced to the outbreak, with one known death.²⁵

A sample from October 2020 demonstrates how often churches

19. CDC, *Scientific Brief: SARS-Cov-2 and Potential Airborne Transmission* (May 7, 2021), <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/science/science-briefs/sars-cov-2-transmission.html> (noting that transmission occurs after exposure to respiratory droplets or aerosols and risks increase due to enclosed spaces, inadequate ventilation, or prolonged exposure); Carolyn Barber, *Protecting Against COVID's Aerosol Threat*, *Scientific America* (Oct. 1, 2020), <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/protecting-against-covids-aerosol-threat/>; Kai Kupferschmidt, *Why Do Some COVID-19 Patients Infect Many Others, Whereas Most Don't Spread the Virus at All?* *Science* (May 19, 2020), <https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2020/05/why-do-some-covid-19-patients-infect-many-others-whereas-most-don-t-spread-virus-all>; Martin Z. Bazant & John W.M. Bush, *A Guideline to Limit Indoor Airborne Transmission of COVID-19*, *Proceedings of the National Academic Of Sciences* (Apr. 27, 2021), <https://www.pnas.org/content/118/17/e2018995118>

20. WHO (@WHO), Twitter (July 16, 2020, 11:36 PM), <https://twitter.com/WHO/status/1283787493096202240?s=20>. Epidemiologists in Japan have long warned against the three Cs: closed spaces, crowded places, and close-contact settings where people are talking face-to-face. Office for the Novel Coronavirus Disease Control, Gov't Of Japan, *Avoid the 'Three Cs'!* (2020), <https://corona.go.jp/prevention/pdf/en.cluster2.pdf>.

21. Valentyn Stadnyskiy et al, *The Airborne Lifetime of Small Speech Droplets and their Potential Importance in SARS-CoV-2 Transmission*, 117 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 11875 (June, 2, 2020), <https://www.pnas.org/content/117/22/11875> (“[T]here is a substantial probability that normal speaking causes airborne virus transmission in confined environments.”); Derek Thompson, *Mask Up and Shut Up*, *The Atlantic* (Aug. 31, 2020), <https://www.theatlantic.com/ideas/archive/2020/08/wear-your-mask-and-stop-talking/615796/> (“[C]ompared with yelling, quiet talking reduces aerosols by a factor of five; being completely silent reduces them by a factor of about 50.”).

22. Lea Hamner et al., *High SARS-CoV-2 Attack Rate Following Exposure at a Choir Practice — Skagit County, Washington*, *March 2020*, 69 *Morbidity & Mortality Wkly. Rep.* 606, 607 (2020).

23. Hillary Brueck, *A 30-Minute Conversation May Be One of the Riskiest-COVID-19 Activities*, *Business Insider* (Nov. 3, 2020), <https://www.businessinsider.com/avoid-spreading-coronavirus-stop-talking-so-much-2020-9>; Knvul Sheikh, *Talking Can Generate Coronavirus Droplets That Linger Up to 14 Minutes*, *N.Y. Times* (June 2, 2020), <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/05/14/health/coronavirus-infections.html>.

24. See Caroline Mala Corbin, *Religious Liberty in a Pandemic*, 70 *Duke L. J. Online* 1, 22-23 nn.125-131 (providing examples).

25. Allison James et al., *High COVID-19 Attack Rate Among Attendees at Events at a Church—Arkansas*, *March 2020*, 69 *Morbidity & Mortality Wkly. REP.* 632, 634 tbl. 1 (2020), <https://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/volumes/69/wr/pdfs/mm6920e2-H.pdf>.

served as the locus of super-spreader events.²⁶ More than 200 cases have been linked to church services at the Crossroads Community Church on October 18 in Massachusetts.²⁷ Over 213 positive cases, and 12 deaths, were traced to a North Carolina church's convocations in October.²⁸ In Maine, an October fellowship service at a church resulted in at least 62 cases of COVID-19.²⁹ A worship service on October 11 at Liberty Church in Michigan was the source of at least 74 infections.³⁰

No such severe clusters have been traced to people shopping at stores.³¹ The nature of the excursion differs from worship services, and these differences present a lower risk profile.

First, the typical time spent inside is much shorter. When people shop, they generally enter and leave the store as fast as they can. Worship services are extended affairs. A usual Sunday Catholic Mass takes at least an hour, and other services can be even longer: one plaintiff church's service lasted an hour and forty-five minutes.³²

In his dissent to an earlier Supreme Court decision to uphold California's restrictions, Justice Kavanaugh complained, "Why can someone safely walk down a grocery store aisle but not a pew?"³³ The answer is that that they can but do not: people sit in pews, not walk down them.

Second, people in stores generally try to minimize their interactions as much as possible; a feat made easier by the ability to constantly move around. In addition, the shopping can be done with little or no conversation.

In contrast, the point of in-person religious services is to commune with one's fellow worshippers. Even when social distancing, congregants

26. At this is just a sampling. See, e.g., Nakia McNabb, *At least 18 West Virginia Covid-19 Outbreaks Linked to Church Services, Governor Says*, CNN.COM (Oct. 19, 2020) (describing active Covid-19 outbreaks), <https://www.cnn.com/2020/10/19/us/west-virginia-covid-churches-trnd/index.html>.

27. Kaitlin McKinley Becker, *More Than 200 COVID-19 Cases Linked to Fitchburg Church*, NBC Boston (Nov. 7, 2020), <https://www.nbcboston.com/news/local/more-than-200-covid-19-cases-linked-to-fitchburg-church/2225433/>.

28. AP, *Three More Dead from COVID-19 Outbreak Linked to North Carolina Church*, ABC NEWS (Nov. 22, 2020), <https://wlos.com/news/local/3-more-dead-from-covid-19-outbreak-linked-to-north-carolina-church>.

29. Lauren Abbate, *Maine CDC Closes COVID-19 Outbreak Investigation Into Brooks Church*, Bangor Daily News (Nov. 20, 2020), <https://bangordailynews.com/2020/11/20/news/midcoast/maine-cdc-closes-covid-19-outbreak-investigation-into-brooks-church/>.

30. Krystle Holleman, *One Death Reported after COVID-19 Outbreak at Grand Ledge Church*, WILX10 (Nov. 11, 2020), <https://www.wilx.com/2020/11/11/one-death-reported-after-covid-19-outbreak-at-grand-ledge-church/>.

31. Cf. *Cassell v. Snyders*, 458 F. Supp. 981, 997 (N.D. Ill. 2020) ("There are many examples where religious services have accelerated the pathogen's spread ... In comparison, Plaintiffs have failed to identify a grocery store or liquor store that has acted as a vector for the virus.").

32. *Elim Romanian Pentecostal Church v. Pritzker*, No. 20 C 2782, 2020 WL 2468194, at *4 (N.D. Ill. May 13, 2020).

33. *S. Bay United Pentecostal Church v. Newsom*, 140 S. Ct. 1613, 1615 (2020) (Kavanaugh, J., dissenting).

are still in an open room, perhaps with questionable ventilation, filled with people all around them. Moreover, the fellow worshippers surrounding them are speaking and even singing for an extended period of time. Not surprisingly, the Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health rated the contact intensity of shopping as low and the contact intensity of places of worship as high.³⁴

In sum, the current science suggests that crowded indoor spots where people talk, sing, and socialize for an extended period of time are high risk. While that generally does not describe people at their local shop, it does describe religious services. The bottom line, then, is that mass gatherings and shopping are not analogous in terms of risk. Accordingly, mass gathering bans should satisfy the neutral and generally applicable requirements of *Smith*.

A final note: this analysis assumes a ban that covers all large indoor gatherings, including gatherings inside restaurants, bars and other indoor places where people interact for a prolonged period of time. To exempt restaurants – or casinos – but not houses of worship weakens the state’s defense. Although it should not necessarily defeat it, the Supreme Court recent COVID-19 rulings suggest otherwise.

To allow all mass gatherings except religious worship inexorably leads to the conclusion that the point of the law was to burden religious exercise. It is harder to insist on that conclusion when not only religious gatherings are banned, but a long list of secular gatherings are as well, even if a few secular counterparts are permitted. However, the Supreme Court has held that they will find religious discrimination if there is a single comparable secular activity that has fewer restrictions, even if there are dozens of comparable secular activities that have more restrictions.³⁵ Consequently, the strongest mass gathering bans are comprehensive. If they are, then there is no reason to exclude houses of worship. Unfortunately, this conclusion depends on a Supreme Court getting the comparisons right, and not comparing “apples to watermelons.”³⁶

34. John Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, Public Health Principles for a Phased Re-Opening During Covid-19: Guidance For Governors, 12, 16 (Apr. 17, 2020), https://www.centerforhealthsecurity.org/our-work/pubs_archive/pubs-pdfs/2020/200417-reopening-guidance-governors.pdf. The Guide also rated worship services as “high” in number of contacts, compared to “medium” for retail. *Id.*

35. *Tandon v. Newsom*, 141 S. Ct. 1294, 1296 (2021) (“[G]overnment regulations are not neutral and generally applicable, and therefore trigger strict scrutiny under the Free Exercise Clause, whenever they treat any comparable secular activity more favorably than religious exercise. It is no answer that a State treats some comparable secular businesses or other activities as poorly as or even less favorably than the religious exercise at issue.”).

36. *Cf. Tandon v. Newsom*, 141 S. Ct. 1294, 1298 (2021) (Sotomayor, J., dissenting) (“[T]he law does not require that the State equally treat apples and watermelons.”).

CONCLUSION

Bans on all mass gatherings, including religious ones, should be perfectly constitutional in the midst of a pandemic. The Supreme Court once noted that “The right to practice religion freely does not include liberty to expose the community . . . to communicable disease.”³⁷ Whether that sentiment still holds true is now an open question. Our constitutional rights are precious, but none of them should be absolute--especially if exercising them endangers others.

37. *Prince v. Massachusetts*, 321 U.S. 158, 166–67 (1944).

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